

DEVELOPMENT OF ECONOMIC ACTIVITIES OF ENTERPRISES ON THE BASIS OF DIGITIZATION

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ABSTRACT: The article discusses the ways and methods of developing economic activities of enterprises based on digitalization. The article summarizes the experience of using information systems in foreign logistics companies, their typology and functionality. The definition of the concept of "intelligent logistics" is formulated, which contains a description of the essence of the term, describing its specific features and effects achieved as a result of the processes of the same name.

Keywords: Digitalization, logistics, enterprises, innovation technologies, information systems, logistics companies, logistic activities, development

Logistics has a thousand-year-old ancient history in mankind. The ancient Egyptian pyramid, built from numerous wars, is the same in the form of trade, as well as places for storing and transporting materials, the same form of logistics with its longterm evolution. Especially in the last 30 years, the logistics industry is the tremendous changes of the times we have been to.

Companies ahead of the competition for overseas markets and cheap production, but to find the factory prior to the increasingly complex supply chain of efficient management is critical to success would have been. However, the transportation with the development of computers and the Internet is a revolutionary technology introduced in the complex supply chain and logistics management approach to further development as this transformation has been.

The rise of new technologies, the growth of electronic business, the arrival of new companies to the service sector, and improved levels of customer service are just some of the factors that attest to the changes in the logistics sector in recent years. In light of these changes, a good

business model is essential to the success of any company. New logistics models must therefore take into account this current competitive landscape to create deliver and capture value.

Companies in all sectors are now embracing digital technologies and reshaping their models to meet the new trends of digital transformation. They develop new processes or modify existing ones, create a new corporate culture, and even implement a completely new customer experience to meet the changing needs of consumers and market demands.

Digital transformation in logistics and transport helps companies in the industry to take advantage of new technologies and remain competitive in an ever-expanding market.

The high adoption of digital technologies in the field helps transportation and logistics companies to solve a wide range of problems, from asset underutilization and supply chain inefficiencies to increasing connectivity and visibility across different systems.

Digital transformation is the process of changing products, services, and entire business models through the adoption of digital technologies. The good news about the transportation sector is that it used to be viewed as backward but today figures among the pioneers in terms of digitalization. But only large logistics companies can afford to create internal IT departments. Digitizing the entire spectrum of technological processes is also capital-intensive. This is why large organizations are more likely to implement digital transformation initiatives.

Logistics is not just about digital tracking or calculating good flows. We are also talking about physical processes that need to be automated. This is where robotics and the innovation technologies come into play. While some innovations require large investments, small logistics companies can also use digital tools to rethink their business models and create value for their customers. The technology can help transport and logistics companies solve problems related to the connectivity and visibility of various devices and systems, insufficient use of assets, or insufficient efficiency in the supply chain. The transport sector is constantly facing many different challenges related to:

- connectivity and visibility between different devices and systems,
- underutilization of assets,
- lack of efficiency in the supply chain.

Digital transformation initiatives enable such companies to build a robust platform that addresses these challenges. Limited use of technology can have a negative impact on the efficiency, productivity, and market growth of a business today. Specialists working in the field of logistics point to the lack of necessary skills and experience in the entire supply chain. This is why companies often have to rely on external resources to implement digital transformation. Transport and logistics prioritize the values of optimization, speed, efficiency and timeliness. With all industries now experiencing a technological explosion, it is only natural that digital transformation has become a necessity for the transportation industry.

Digital transformation can bring benefits to companies from the logistics sector in several areas.

Increase speed and time. Speed and time play a crucial role in the transport sector. Minimum time and high speed form the main competitive advantage for companies in this industry. Digital transformation initiatives that use Robotic process automation (RPA) to automate timeconsuming processes can greatly help companies keep up with their competitors. By providing services to customers faster, they position themselves as leaders in their industry.

Connecting between different devices. Another important advantage of digital conversion is that it allows you to create hyper-communication between devices using sensors. This is where technologies like the Internet of Things come into play. They allow companies to combine devices that use sensors to transmit critical information over a single network.

By enabling physical objects to interact and communicate with other things and business users involved in decision - making, digital transformation has the potential to disrupt the entire sector. Connected devices can also speed up processes and help increase the reaction rate.

Business analytics. By digitizing transport logistics processes, companies are seeing an increase in data volumes. Creating this amount of data means that organizations need to learn modern technologies, such as data analysis and business intelligence. Data-driven decision-making requires support from cognitive computing, artificial intelligence solutions, and machine learning. This is where digital transformation can help. It allows companies to overcome various business challenges, such as:

- supply chain management, process
- optimization, cost
- control, and customer service improvement.

Visibility across all key factors. Creating huge amounts of data involves unique challenges and complexities. To unlock the value of data, companies need effective tools and technologies. Logistics, transportation, and supply chain companies are launching digital transformation strategies that focus on managing the visibility of factors that influence their decisionmaking process.

With state-of-the-art analytics tools, companies can now visualize data and take advantage of state-of-the-art dashboards with self-service capabilities that offer digital transformation at the user level. Such tools present a large amount of data in a meaningful, concise and pleasant way so that it can be used by managers when making decisions.

Improving the efficiency of machinery and equipment. Transport and logistics companies must ensure that the goods arrive at the right place, at the right time and in the best possible condition. This is why it is so important that all machines and equipment remain in working order and do not wear out unexpectedly. This scenario can lead to downtime and delays. Digital transformation helps companies constantly monitor their equipment and warns those even months before a part breaks down. Innovative technologies such as data analytics, cloud computing, and Internet of Things sensors, together with machine learning algorithms, provide a

powerful trend called predictive maintenance that allows businesses to avoid downtime caused by equipment damage.

Blockchain

Companies seeking to improve the visibility of shipments and increase confidence in the movement of international cargo can already take advantage of the blockchain. Blockchain-based innovations such as smart contracts and decentralized applications (dapps) enable secure data distribution, decentralization, and validation. Blockchain technology is finding more and more applications in the visibility of the supply chain.

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)

According to Accenture, augmented reality is revolutionizing the picking, packaging and commissioning processes in warehouses and cross-dock areas, providing logistics companies with a competitive advantage. Virtual reality can be used to significantly improve the delivery process, making it safer and more efficient by superimposing important information directly on drivers' windshields. This way, drivers don't even have to look at their handheld device to see alternative routes, traffic jams, and blocked roads. Virtual reality can even improve the quality of service when drivers are at the point of delivery. For example, drivers can use virtual reality glasses to view information about weight, contents, and handling instructions to ensure safe delivery of packages.

Robotic Process Automation (RPA)

The process automation software is expected to increase the level of automation to almost 100% in areas such as customer billing and the transport planning process. Using robotic process automation, transportation companies optimize their processes, reduce costs, and simply provide a better customer experience.

Business Intelligence platforms

Digital platforms offering a wide range of data analysis features will make the entire supply chain much more clear and transparent. This, in turn, will allow companies to continue optimizing their activities in other business areas, such as sales.

Big Data Analytics

Big data analytics solutions will provide an information ecosystem that allows businesses to improve the efficiency of their organizations and avoid common problems associated with underutilization of assets.

Conclusion. There is no denying that what used to be one of the most traditional and technologically backward sectors is now at the forefront of digital transformation. Transport and logistics companies are taking advantage of completely new solutions to improve operational efficiency, eliminate unnecessary costs and improve the quality of customer service. They invest in digital transformation strategies because it is the only way to survive and succeed in the current market, gaining a competitive advantage for many years to come.

REFERENCES:

1. Mulyadinov, F. (2021). Digital Economy Is A Guarantee Of Government And Society Development. *Ilkogretim Online*, 20(3), 1474-1479.
2. Rakhimov, M., Yuldashev, A., & Solidjonov, D. (2021). THE ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF E-LEARNING PLATFORMS AND MONITORING KNOWLEDGE OF STUDENTS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(9), 308-314.
3. Андреева Л. А., Зенкин А. А. (2019). Концептуальные вопросы развития стандартизации логистической деятельности. *Вестник транспортной информации*, 4(286), 3-11.

4. Аптекман А., Калабин В., Клинцов В., Кузнецова Е., Кулагин В., Ясеновец И. (2017). Цифровая Россия: Новая реальность. McKinsey & Company.
5. Белозерцева Н. П. И Ярайкина М. С. (2013). Анализ тенденций развития рынка грузовых перевозок в Приморском крае. Территория новых возможностей. Вестник ВГУЭС, 1(19), 150-155.
6. Дмитриев А. В. (2019). Цифровые технологии прослеживаемости грузов в транспортно-логистических системах. Стратегические решения и управление рисками, 1, 20-26.
7. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339797544> Digitization As A Tool F or The Logistics Framework Development
8. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/325040610> Logistics and Digitization
9. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/management-of-the-innovative-development-ofan-enterprise-based-on-the-logistic-approach>
10. Akhmedovich, M. A., & Fazliddin, A. (2020). Current State Of Wind Power Industry. The American Journal of Engineering and Technology, 2(09), 32-36. <https://doi.org/10.37547/tajet/Volume02Issue09-05>